

Organizational Silence: An Obstacle to Organizational Learning

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this research is to study Organizational Silence (OS) as one of the biggest barriers to Organizational Learning (OL) at the Telecommunications sector in Egypt.

Design/methodology/approach: To assess OS, refer to (OS questionnaire, Schechtman, 2008; Brinsfield, 2009), and OL (OL questionnaire American Society for Training and Development, 2002). Out of the 290 questionnaires that were distributed to employees, 235 usable questionnaires were returned, a response rate of 81%. Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) was used to confirm the research hypotheses.

Findings: The research has found that there is a significant relationship between OS and OL. Also, the research has found that OS directly affects OL. In other words, OS is one of the biggest barriers to OL at the Telecommunications sector in Egypt.

Practical implications: This research contributes to stimulate scientific research, particularly in terms of testing the model content, as well as studying the research variables and the factors affecting them. In addition, this research pointed to the need for organizations to adopt a culture which encourages and urges employees to speak in the labor issues and the non-silence in order for the administration to be able to realize these issues and try to solve them first hand in order to prevent their aggravation.

Originality/value: Although the phenomenon of silence is expected in organizations, there is little empirical evidence in the literature aimed at defining, analyzing, and coping with it. Silence climate has an impact on the ability of organizations to detect errors and learn. Therefore, organizational effectiveness is negatively affected. This research aims to measure the effect of OS on OL. Based on the findings of this research, some important implications are discussed.

Keywords: organizational silence, organizational learning

1. Introduction

Organizational Silence (OS) is a reflection of many dimensions and variables within business organizations, including the reluctance of staff to submit their views and suggestions for the development of the organization, in addition to lack of interaction with the important work issues of the organization (Bogosion, 2012).

Organizations need employees who express their opinions and break the culture of silence. Also, people choose organizations to work that provide a voice for their staff. For organizations which don't have silence culture, both employees and managers are at high level of motivation and performance (Beheshtifar et al., 2012; Schlosser & Zolin 2012).

OS leads to poor Organizational Learning (OL), arguing that employees failed to talk with their superiors about the problems of work. There is also a relationship between OS and job withdrawal, as employee's preference of silence to talking is a matter of time before making the decision of withdrawing or leaving (Brinsfield, 2009).

Silence obstructs the effective OL. This constitutes a barrier to organizational change and development and suppresses pluralism, hence innovation and creativity (Morrison & Milliken, 2000; Milliken & Morrison, 2003).

OS and OL are very important subjects for organizations to reach the desired objectives. In this context, our study focuses on the relationship between OS and OL. The study is structured as follows: Section one is introductory. Section two presents the literature review. Section three discusses the research methodology. Section four presents the hypotheses testing. Section five explains the research findings. Research recommendations will take place at section six. Section seven handles the research implications. Limitations and future research will take place at section eight. Conclusion will be provided at the last section.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Silence

Silence is associated with many virtues: modesty, respect for others, prudence, decorum. People silence themselves to avoid embarrassment, confrontation and other perceived dangers (Perlow & Williams, 2003).

Silence is an active, conscious, intentional and purposeful behavior. Early definitions of silence equated it with “loyalty” and the assumption that nothing was wrong if concerns were not being voiced. But researchers today have shown that a climate of silence can work against desired organizational outcomes (Pinder & Harlos, 2001; Aylsworth, 2008).

There are three silence dimensions. Firstly, silence can be intentional. Employees remain silent even if they are aware of the problem and know of a better solution. Secondly, silence can be defense mechanism. Employees can remain silent in order to protect their personal interests or not to openly contradict others. Thirdly, silence can be a collective decision of employees; a collective reaction of not sharing ideas, thoughts, or knowledge with others (Park & Keil, 2009).

Silence can convey approval and sharing or disfavor and opposition, thus becoming a pressure mechanism for both individuals and organizations (Bagheri, et al. 2012).

2.2. Types of Silence

There are four types of silence. They are acquiescent silence, defensive silence, prosocial silence, and protective silence (Pinder & Harlos 2001; Van Dyne, et al., 2003; Briensfield 2009; Perlow & Repeing; 2009; Cakici 2010; Alparslan 2010; Bogosian, 2012).

2.2.1. Acquiescent Silence

Acquiescent silence (AS) relates to occasions where employees chose not to express relevant ideas, information and opinions based on resignation which suggests disengaged behaviour (Kahn 1990).

AS is synonymous with employees who are essentially disengaged and are unwilling to take steps to enact change (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

AS is described as an intentionally passive silent behavior. AS is withholding relevant ideas, information, or opinions, based on resignation. AS suggests disengaged behavior that is more passive than active (Van Dyne, et al. 2003).

AS is the withholding of information, views, opinions and ideas in the face of developments in the organizations.

AS is a passive behavior. In the case of AS, employees approve the status quo, do not want to speak up much, and do not attempt to change the organizational circumstances. This attitude requires remaining silent purposefully and not being involved in developments. The reason that lies behind employees' failure to speak out is the belief that it will not make a difference even if they do speak out (Karacaoglu & Cingoz, 2008).

2.2.2. Defensive Silence

Defensive silence (DS) is based on an employee's personal fear of speaking up. This can be termed as quiescent silence (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

DS is described as deliberate omission of work related information based on fear of reprisal. DS is intentional and proactive behavior that is intended to protect the self from external threats. In contrast to AS, DS is more proactive, involving awareness and consideration of alternatives, followed by a conscious decision to withhold ideas, information, and opinions as the best personal strategy at the moment (Van Dyne, et al., 2003; Karacaoglu & Cingoz, 2008).

2.2.3. Pro Social Silence

Prosocial silence is withholding of work related information for the benefit of others including the organization. Pro Social silence is intentional and proactive behaviour is primarily focused on others. Pro social silence involves conscious decision making by an employee, Pro social silence arises from a concern for others instead of fear of negative personal consequences (Korsgaard et al., 1997).

Pro social silence is the refusal to express ideas, information or opinions so that others in the organization might benefit from it. This silence is motivated by the desire to help others and share the duties. It is considerate and focuses on others (Podkasoff et al., 2000).

Like Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Pro-social Silence is intentional and proactive behavior that is primarily focused on others. Like OCB, Pro-social silence is discretionary behavior that can not be mandated by an organization. Like DS, Pro-social silence is based on awareness and consideration of alternatives and the conscious decision to withhold ideas, information, and opinions (Van Dyne, et al. 2003).

This form of silence is intentional, proactive and other-oriented. In other words, primary priority of an employee who decides to remain silent is not himself but the external factors such as the organization or his colleagues (Van Dyne et.al., 2003).

2.2.4. Protective Silence

Protective silence is where employees can be silent and accept decisions of higher level management. One of the most important causes of silence is the good relationship between the organization and employees. Therefore, employees prefer to be silent instead of telling what is wrong in their organizations (Morrison & Milliken, 2003).

It is not an only image problem, it is also a problem related to maintaining their good relationships within the organization. (Perlow & Reppenning, 2009, Alparslan 2010).

2.3. Organizational Silence

OS can remain prevalent when management proudly speak of empowerment and the development of more open lines communication (Lawler 1992; Spreitzer 1996).

OS has been defined as “consciously refraining from expressing ideas, information and beliefs about work.” OS may result in lack of feedback, information and ideas and alternatives analysis. OS occurs when employees intentionally withhold their opinions and knowledge about organizational problems (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

OS is a collective act of employees consciously not sharing their knowledge, beliefs, thoughts, ideas, and experiences with the management about the issues for their work or to improve their working environment (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

OS is a reaction of employees; although they are normally able to bring and sustain change to workplace, they remain reluctant to share their behavioral, cognitive, or emotional assessments on workplace related issues. In other words, OS is the withholding of any form of genuine expression about the individual's behavioral, cognitive and/or affective evaluations of his or her organizational circumstances to persons who are perceived to be capable of effecting change or redress (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

OS means the presence of a common perception among employees limiting their participation in providing their knowledge about the issues and policies of the Organization (Nennete, 2002).

OS is a reflection of the forces affecting the relationships between individuals and groups and regulations governing these relationships which prevent staff of talking about the organization's problems (Avan et al, 2003).

OS occurs due to the fundamental beliefs held by managers including; manager's fear of negative feedback and a set of implicit beliefs held by managers that lead to organizational structures, processes and managerial practices that impede the level of silence within an organization (Rodriguez, 2004).

OS may take various forms, such as collective silence in meetings, low levels of participation in suggestion schemes, and low levels of collective voice (Huang, et al., 2005).

OS refers to the collective phenomenon of comment or to very little action in response to the major issues facing the organization (Henriksen & Dayton, 2006).

OS is a variable which can prevail about barriers to effectiveness, commitment and performance (Beer 2009).

There are some problems caused by OS, employees' inability of producing new ideas and their non-progressiveness are significant (Kahveci, 2010).

OS leads to dissonance and this in turn results in low motivation, satisfaction and commitment. ES can lead to stress, denial, dissatisfaction and disconnection between the staff (Nikolaou et al., 2011; Nikmaram, et al., 2012).

2.4. Organizational Silence Factors

2.4.1. Support of the Top Management of Silence

The role of top management is instrumental in the success of the business organizations. The availability of a high degree of confidence in the administration reduces concerns of speaking freely about the problems and issues of labor. Climate of confidence in the top management reduces the feelings of uncertainty (Weber & Weber, 2001).

The attitudes and values of the top management may contribute greatly to the formation of a climate of silence, as some organizations prohibit employees from saying what they know or feel (Argyris, 1997).

The top management practices may lead to increased levels of silence within the organization. These practices are represented in two factors (Morrison & Milliken, 2000):

2.4.1.1. Managers' Fear of Negative Feedback

The top management may be afraid of getting negative feedback information from the subordinates, as it may feel threatened as a result of this information, particularly, if they involve its members personally or their work (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

2.4.1.2. Managers' Implicit Beliefs

Silence increases when the top management is in an ivory tower prohibiting it from seeing the actual reality because of lack of access to information, or due to welcoming the good information rather than, the negative (Van, Dyne, et al, 2003).

Thus, the support of the top management of silence leads employees not to talk about work issues (Milliken, et al., 2003).

2.4.2. Lack of Communication Opportunities

Contact is essential to the effectiveness of any organization. It represents the transfer of information verbally or using other means for the purpose of persuasion and influencing the behavior of others. Among the most important functions of the communication process is that it provides individuals with the necessary information for the purpose of decision-making, as it represents an outlet to express feelings, opinions and trends. It is an important means to satisfy social needs of individuals (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

The more contact opportunities within the organization, the greater participation and expression of opinion on issues and problems of the work (Smidts, et al., 2001).

2.4.3. Support of Supervisor for Silence

The supervisor's behavior creates a microcosm climate of silence at the level of the department where he works, where subordinates do not trust that supervisors will not directly or indirectly punish them because of their talk on their mistakes in the work. Therefore, subordinates tend to silence (Spreitzer, 1996; Sugarman, 2001).

The supervisory relations have a tremendous impact on the performance and career paths of subordinates as well as on rewards from the organization (Sparrowe & Liden, 2005).

The relationship of supervisor's strength and stature to silence or talking can be analyzed in two ways: on the one hand, the subordinate may tend to talk more than keep silent with a strong supervisor, because this subordinate believes that the supervisor has the ability to resolve any problem or issue related to work. Here, subordinate find it useful to talk in the presence of a supervisor who has the powers to solve work problems within the organization (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

On the other hand, the freedom to express dissenting opinion may be restricted when working under the leadership of a supervisor with prestige and power, because the subordinate tends to the option of silence due to fear of the negative impact of expressing the dissent opinion (Turner & Pratkanis, 1998).

Power and status of the supervisor can increase or decrease the silence of subordinates. It can be concluded that silence could increase in the presence of a powerful supervisor (Edmondson, 1996).

2.4.4. Official Authority

Officialdom is the degree by which the activities carried out by employees are formed within the organization, through the adoption of several measures. These procedures are usually written, and associated with the presence of work evidences and records identifying the behavior of employees, the tasks to be achieved and regulations controlling the work progress within the organization (Moorhead & Criffin, 2004).

Officialdom is based on the strength of the position or location in the organizational structure (Ashford et al., 1998).

2.4.5. Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions

The fear of the reaction may lead employees to believe that talking about work problems might deprive them of their jobs or upgrade to higher positions within the organization (Milliken, et al, 2003).

2.5. Organizational Silence Effects

There are several implications of OS, as silence is of a significant impact on individuals and the organization (Bogosian, 2012).

Silence affects the decision-making process of the organization, in the sense that the quality of the decision depends on the need to have knowledge of the employees' suggestions, and vice versa (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

There are negative impacts of OS. They are (1) poor participation of employees in decision-making because of the lack of the channels or opportunities of communication, (2) reducing dealing with conflict or dispute in an effective manner, and (3) weakness of the employees' capacity to learning and self-development (Low et al., 2002).

The effects of OS are not limited to the organization, as it can negatively affect the behavior of individuals working in the organization. These effects are represented in (1) the individual's feeling unappreciated, (2) lack of the individual's ability to control, and (3) the individual suffering from cognitive dissonance. This is because silence makes it difficult to the individual to strike a balance between his beliefs and behaviors (Hazen, 2006).

OS correlates negatively with three dimensions of organizational trust (trust in the organization, trust in leadership, trust in the supervisor). This means that the more silence means less trust (Nikolaous, et al., 2011).

OS has a negative impact on the removal of inadequacies and mistakes occurring in the organizational activities as well as on the establishment of a healthy feedback mechanism. In an organization without feedback mechanisms, mistakes turn into a mechanism of carrying out activities or become more severe (Milliken & Morrison, 2003).

2.6. Organizational Learning

The term "learning" in English, according to Oxford (1960) means "to obtain the knowledge or skill by study, experience, thinking, preservation, remembering, taking science or finding out manner.

In French, according to (Robert, 1983), "Apprendre" denotes telling something, acquiring knowledge by mental work or mediated experience.

Learning does not mean education, as education is a deliberate process and needs a teacher and the recipient, while learning can be deliberate or unintentional (Moorhead & Griffin, 1995).

Learning is an effective way to achieve the goals of individuals to obtain rewards, prestige, power and/or strength. It is an effective tool to manage change (Robson, 1997).

Learning is a process of interaction between the individual and the organization through mutual influence (Torrington & Hall, 1998).

Learning is a critical variable in the organization's ability to successfully deal with the ever-changing environment, and OL is vital to decision-making at the organization as a means of access to information and knowledge besides absorbing and processing them (Nath, 2002).

OL has been regarded as one of the strategic means of achieving long-term organizational success. Reviews of the OL literature have noted a tremendous increase in research interest over the last two decades (Bapuji & Crossan, 2004). OL has become an increasingly important area recently (Liao & Wu, 2009).

Most researchers have pointed to the importance of OL for the individual and the organization. Learning contributes to the development of a person by helping him recognize and understand others, interact with them and improve his skills in human relations. This improves the experience of life in order to achieve compatibility with the cultural, social and environmental requirements (Argyris, 1978).

A lot of the pioneers were interested in the concept of OL (Argyris & Schon 1978, Senge 1990).

OL represents the bridge between work and creativity, playing an important role in getting the competitive advantage of the organization (Brown & Dguid, 1991).

OL is the means through which old ideas are superseded and replaced with new ones. It is listening to others and heeding their opinions (Jones, 1995).

OL is one of the important sources of sustainable competitive advantage (Fulmer et al., 1998).

OL has been linked to many important organizational outcomes such as the facilitation of innovation (Ahuja & Lampert, 2001), the survival and effectiveness of acquisitions, diversifications and foreign entries (Barkema, et al., 1996; Hayward, 2002), increased customer orientation (Hult, et al., 2000), and the successful implementation of information systems (Caron et al., 1994; Robey & Sahay, 1996).

The organization's ability to learn and adapt to change has become one of the basic conditions for efficiency and survival of the organization. OL and the acquisition and dissemination of knowledge play an important role in improving products and services (Licker, 1997; Allee, 1997).

OL system includes vision, strategy, culture, leadership, structure, systems and processes (Stratigos, 2001).

OL is the means for continuous improvement of efficiency and quality, creativity and responsiveness to customers (Hill & Jonses, 2001).

OL is the need for information and knowledge sharing among employees. Argyris (1977) noted that the failure of employees to speak to their bosses concerning potential problems at work is a frequent impediment to OL. This type of silence, he contends, keeps organizations from recognizing, correcting, and learning from their mistakes (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

Employee willingness to speak-up is critical for learning at the team level as well. The perceived ease of speaking-up is important for the facilitation of new practices in teams. According to Edmondson, teams whose members speak-up with observations, concerns, and questions are better able to learn new routines than those in which members are unwilling to say what they are thinking (Edmondson, 2003).

A primary difference between individual and OL seems to reside not only in the process of learning per se, but also in the method by which knowledge is stored and communicated to other organizational members (King et al., 2008).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable of OS. There is one dependent variable of OL. It shows the rational links among the variables. The research model is as shown in the following figure.

Figure (1)
Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

3.2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

The research framework suggests that OS has an impact on OL. OS as measured consisted of support of the top management of silence, lack of communication opportunities, support of supervisor for silence, official authority, and subordinate's fear of negative reactions (Schechtman, 2008; Brinsfield, 2009).

OL is measured in terms of the dynamics of learning, conversion of the organization, employee empowerment, knowledge management, and the application of technology (American Society for Training and Development, 2002).

3.2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature reviews that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between OS and OL. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment. The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees in order to identify the relationship between OS and OL. The researcher found several indicators notably the important and vital role that could be played by OS. As a result of the discussions given above, the research questions are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between OS (support of the top management of silence) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between OS (lack of communication opportunities) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- Q3: What is the statistically significant relationship between OS (support of supervisor for silence) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- Q4: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between OS (official authority) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- Q5: What is the nature of the relationship between OS (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

There are studies in literature that study OS and OL factors separately and within the frame of bilateral relation but there is no study that examines these two factors collectively at the Egyptian environment. This study aims to contribute to the literature by examining the research variables collectively and reveal the interaction between the research variables.

As a result of the discussions given above, the following hypotheses were developed to test the effect of OS on OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

- H1: OS (support of the top management of silence) of employees has no statistically significant effect on OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- H2: OS (lack of communication opportunities) of employees has no statistically significant impact on OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- H3: OS (support of supervisor for silence) of employees has no statistically significant influence on OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- H4: OS (official authority) of employees has no statistically significant effect on OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.
- H5: OS (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) of employees has no statistically significant impact OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

3.3. Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt. The total population is 1196 employees. Determination of respondent sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

The number of samples obtained by 290 employees at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt is as presented in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Telecommunication Sector in Egypt	Nurses	Percentage	Sample Size
1. Telecom Egypt	812	68%	290X 68% = 197
2. Vodafone	134	11%	290X 11% = 32
3. Mobinil	128	11%	290X 11% = 32
4. Télécommunications	122	10%	290X 10% = 29
Total	1196	100%	290X 100% = 290

Source: Personnel Department at the Telecommunication Sector in Egypt, 2015

Table (2) provides the features of the respondents at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt who participated in the survey.

Table (2) Frequency Distribution Table of Demographics

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
1- Sex	Male	155	66%
	Female	80	34%
	Total	235	100%
2- Marital Status	Single	120	51.1%
	Married	115	48.9%
	Total	235	100%
3- Age	Under 30	50	21.3%
	From 30 to 45	85	36.2%
	Above 45	100	42.6%
	Total	235	100%
4- Educational Level	Secondary school	50	21.3%
	University	85	36.2%
	Post Graduate	100	42.6%
	Total	235	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	60	25.5%
	From 5 to 10	100	42.6%
	More than 10	75	31.9%
	Total	235	100%

Source: Personnel Department at the Telecommunication in Egypt, 2015

3.4. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the relationship between OS and OL at Telecommunication sector in Egypt. A survey research method was used to collect data. The questionnaire included three questions, relating to OS, OL, and demographic information of employees at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt. Data collection took two months. Survey responses were 81%, 235 completed surveys out of the 290 distributed.

3.5. Data Collection Tools

3.5.1. Organizational Silence Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by Schechtman, 2008; and Brinsfield, 2009 in measuring OS, which has been divided into five elements (support of the top management of silence, lack of communication opportunities, support of supervisor for silence, official authority, and subordinate's fear of negative reactions).

The 27-item scale OS section is based on Schechtman, 2008; and Brinsfield, 2009. There were five items measuring support of the top management of silence, six items measuring lack of communication opportunities, five items measuring support of supervisor for silence, five items measuring official authority, and six items measuring subordinate's fear of negative reactions. The survey form is used as the main tool for data collection in measuring OS at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

Responses are categorized using a 5-point Likert Scale for each statement, ranging from (1) “very ineffective”, (2) “ineffective”, (3) “neither effective nor ineffective”, (4) “effective”, and (5) “very effective”.

3.5.2. Organizational Learning Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by American Society for Training and Development (2002) in measuring OL, which has been divided into five main components (the dynamics of learning, conversion of the organization, employee empowerment, knowledge management, and the application of technology). The 25-item scale OL section is based on American Society for Training and Development (2002). There were five items measuring the dynamics of learning, five items measuring conversion of the organization, five items measuring employee empowerment, six items measuring knowledge management, and four items measuring the application of technology.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

3.6. Data Analysis

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach's alpha or ACC, (2) (MRA), and (3) F- test and T-test. All these tests are found in SPSS.

4. Hypotheses Testing

4.1. Evaluating Reliability

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, the reliability of OS and OL were assessed to reduce errors of measuring and maximizing constancy of these scales. To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach's alpha test was conducted. Table (3) shows the reliability results for OS and OL. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were therefore excellent, according to Langdridge's (2004) criteria.

Table (3) Reliability of OS and OL

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
OS	Support of the top Management of Silence	5	0.9480
	Lack of Communication Opportunities	6	0.9259
	Support of Supervisor for Silence	5	0.8945
	Official Authority	5	0.8746
	Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions	6	0.8778
	Total Measurement	27	0.9819
OL	The Dynamics of Learning	5	0.9143
	Conversion of the Organization	5	0.6546
	Employee Empowerment	5	0.9747
	Knowledge Management	6	0.9728
	The Application of Technology	4	0.8799
	Total Measurement	25	0.9429

Regarding Table (3), the 27 items of OS are reliable because the ACC is 0.9819. Support of the top management of silence, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9480. Lack of communication opportunities, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9259. Furthermore, support of supervisor for silence, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8945. For official authority, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8746. Subordinate's fear of negative reactions, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8778. Thus, the internal consistency of OS can be acceptable.

According to Table (3), the 25 items of OL are reliable because the ACC is 0.9429. The dynamics of learning, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9143. Conversion of the organization, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.6546. Furthermore, employee empowerment which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9747. Knowledge management, which consists of

6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9728. The application of technology, which consists of 4 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8799. Thus, the internal consistency of OL can be acceptable.

Accordingly, two scales were defined, OS (27 variables), where ACC represented about 0.9819, and OL (25 variables), where ACC represented 0.9429.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The researcher calculated means and standard deviations for each variable and created a correlation matrix of all variables used in hypothesis testing. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation values related to dependent and independent variables of this study and correlation coefficients between these variables are given in Table (4).

Table (4) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of Constructs

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Support of the top management of silence	3.37	0.935	1					
2. Lack of communication opportunities	3.50	0.851	0.966**	1				
3. Support of Supervisor for silence	3.42	0.870	0.963**	0.935**	1			
4. Official Authority	3.50	0.815	0.975**	0.953**	0.961**	1		
5. Subordinate's fear of negative reactions	3.35	0.809	0.967**	0.966**	0.930**	0.938**	1	
6. Organizational Learning	3.76	0.816	0.494**	0.484**	0.476**	0.531**	0.463**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

According to Table (4), the reasons of the employees' remaining silent was generated according to the respondents' answers. In order to determine what reasons affect employees to remain silent at work, reasons were grouped under five factors. They are (1) support of the top management of silence, (2) lack of communication opportunities, (3) support of supervisor for silence, (4) official authority, and (5) subordinate's fear of negative reactions.

Based on Table (4), the first issue examined was the different facets of organizational silence. Among the various facets of organizational silence, those who responded identified the presence of a official authority (M=3.50, SD=0.815). This was followed by lack of communication opportunities (M=3.50, SD=0.851), support of supervisor for silence (M=3.42, SD=0.870), support of the top management of silence (M=3.37, SD=0.935), and subordinate's fear of negative reactions (M=3.35, SD=0.809).

The second issue examined was the different facets of OL (the dynamics of learning, conversion of the organization, employee empowerment, knowledge management, and the application of technology). Most of the respondents identified the overall OL (M=3.76, SD=0.816).

According to Table (4), OS dimensions have negative and significant relation with OL dimensions. The correlation between OS (support of the top management of silence) and OL is 0.494. As for OS (lack of communication opportunities) and OL, the value is 0.484 whereas OS (support of supervisor for silence) and OL show correlation value of 0.476. As for OS (official authority) and OL, the value is 0.531 whereas OS (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and OL show correlation value of 0.463.

Finally, Table (4) proves that there is a significant and negative correlation between OS and OL. So our hypothesis is supported and it can be said that there is a significant and negative correlation between OS and OL.

4.3. Organizational Silence (Support of the top Management of Silence) and OL

The relationship between OS (support of the top management of silence) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OS (support of the top management of silence) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

Table (5) proves that there is a relationship between OS (support of the top management of silence) and OL at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R^2 , the 5 independent variables of support of the top management of silence can explain 29.7% of the total differentiation in OL level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of OS (support of the top management of silence) and OL is obtained. Because MCC is 0.545, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (5) MRA Results for OS (Support of the top Management of Silence) and OL

The Variables of OS (Support of the top Management of Silence)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Organization's management believes that its role is limited to the implementation of instructions.	0.359**	0.497	0.247
2. The organization is not interested in encouraging employees to express their opinions or suggestions concerning aspects of the work.	0.461*	0.493	0.243
3. Management of the organization does not tend to serious discussion of the views and suggestions of employees.	0.296*	0.375	0.140
4. Management of the organization does not express gratitude to workers for their opinions and suggestions for useful work.	0.187*	0.422	0.178
5. I do not feel comfortable when management of the organization is involved in solving a problem belonging to me personally.	0.168	0.463	0.214
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.545 0.297 19.315 5, 229 3.78 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

4.4. Organizational Silence (Lack of Communication Opportunities) and OL

The relationship between OS (lack of communication opportunities) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OS (lack of communication opportunities) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

Table (6) MRA Results for OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities) and OL

The Variables of OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities)	Beta	R	R ²
1. There is no exchange of information between various departments and divisions within the organization.	0.152	0.381	0.145
2. The chances of communication between employees in other departments are not enough	0.086	0.307	0.094
3. Management of the organization does not notify the staff with the organization's important problems and issues.	0.284*	0.375	0.140
4. There is not enough channels of communication between employees and senior management of the organization.	0.470**	0.497	0.247
5. Management of the organization does not bother to hold meetings to discuss issues and matters relating to work.	0.241	0.493	0.243
6. My superiors at work do not possess the good skills needed for listening to my views and suggestions.	0.193*	0.422	0.178
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.545 0.296 16.014 6, 228 <u>3.01</u> 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

As Table (6) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.545. This means that OL has been significantly explained by the 6 independent variables of lack of communication opportunities.

Furthermore, the R² of 0.296 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 29.6%. It is evident that the six independent variables justified 29.6% of the total factors of OL. Hence, 70.4% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.5. Organizational Silence (Support of Supervisor for Silence) and OL

The relationship between OS (support of supervisor for silence) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OS (support of supervisor for silence) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

Table (7) MRA Results for OS (Support of Supervisor for Silence) and OL

The Variables of OS (Support of Supervisor for Silence)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I hesitate to speak freely with my direct manager concerning a problem at work.	0.253**	0.448	0.200
2. My direct manager does not care about any negative information about my performance.	0.224	0.463	0.214
3. My direct manager sees any criticism against him a sort of challenging him.	0.510*	0.493	0.243
4. My direct manager suspects the source of my information concerning my performance at work.	0.066	0.422	0.179
5. My direct manager sees the difference in opinion on the problems of working longer unhelpful.	0.099	0.181	0.032
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.521 0.271 17.027 5, 229 <u>2.63</u> 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

Table (7) proves that there is a relationship between OS (support of supervisor for silence) and OL. As a result of the value of R², the 5 independent variables of support of supervisor for silence can explain 27.1% of the total differentiation in OL level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of OS (support of supervisor for silence) and OL is obtained. Because MCC is 0.521, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.6. Organizational Silence (Official Authority) and OL

The relationship between OS (official authority) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OS (official authority) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

Table (8) MRA Results for OS (Official Authority) and OL

The Variables of OS (Official Authority)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My direct manager depends mainly on the official authority to influence subordinates.	0.252*	0.497	0.247
2. My direct manager draws on the method of threatening with punishment to guide the behavior of subordinates.	0.279*	0.493	0.243
3. My direct manager accepts excuses of subordinates with difficulty when they commit negligence in their work.	0.194*	0.375	0.140
4. My direct manager directs the behavior of subordinates through compliance with laws and regulations.	0.143	0.422	0.178
5. My direct manager complies with laws and regulations in force when solving problems of subordinates.	0.198**	0.379	0.143
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.571 0.326 22.111 5, 229 <u>3.78</u> 0.000	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

Table (8) proves that there is a relationship between OS (official authority) and OL at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R², the 5 independent variables of official authority can explain 32.6% of the total differentiation in OL level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of OS (official authority) and OL is obtained. Because MCC is 0.571, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.7. Organizational Silence (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions) and OL

The relationship between OS (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OS (subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and OL at the Telecommunication sector in Egypt.

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.506. This means that OL has been significantly explained by the 6 independent variables of subordinate's fear of negative reactions.

Furthermore, the R² of 0.257 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 25.7%. It is evident that the six independent variables justified 25.7% of the total factors of OL. Hence, 74.3% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (9) MRA Results for OS (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions) and OL

The Variables of OS (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I feel afraid to inform my direct manager with the problems of work in the organization.	0.012	0.189	0.035
2. I don't tend to talking about the negative working conditions for fear of being held accountable.	0.616**	0.493	0.243
3. I prefer to stay silent in order to avoid conflicts or disagreements with superiors.	0.062	0.463	0.214
4. I prefer to stay silent for fear of breaking my relationships with my colleagues.	0.037	0.265	0.070
5. I prefer to stay silent not to be considered a problem-maker.	0.206*	0.375	0.140
6. My speaking of work problems could be harmful to my personal interests.	0.120	0.422	0.178
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.506 0.257 13.111 6, 228 <u>3.01</u> 0.000	
* P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

5. Research Findings

The present study on analyzing the relationship between OS (support of the top management of silence, lack of communication opportunities, support of supervisor for silence, official authority, subordinate's fear of negative reactions) and OL at Telecommunications sector in Egypt revealed the following results:

1. There is a significant relationship between OS and OL at the Telecommunications sector in Egypt. OS plays an important role in influencing OL. Also, OS contributes significantly to OL. In other words, OS is one of the biggest barriers to OL at the Telecommunications sector in Egypt.
2. This study concluded that the OS was negatively related with OL at the Telecommunications sector in Egypt. Overall findings from this study suggested that OS does affect OL. Another study conducted by (Brinsfield, 2009), concluded that OS leads to poor OL. Employees failed to talk with their superiors about the problems of work, which is often a constraint for OL, because silence prevents the organization from correcting mistakes or learning from them. There is also a relationship between OS and job withdrawal, as employee's preference of silence to talking is a matter of time before making the decision of withdraw or leaving the organization.
3. There is a negative relationship between OS and OL of employees at the Telecommunications sector in Egypt. In other words, OS affects OL. Another study conducted by Morrison & Milliken (2000); Milliken & Morrison, (2003), concluded that silence is important to understand, because it has the potential to undermine the reporting of unethical and illegal practices. This constitutes a barrier to organizational change and development and suppresses pluralism, hence innovation and creativity.

6. Research Recommendations

1. Emphasis on the dissemination of OL culture and embracing the vision of the learning organization that require the creation of a regulatory climate. This supports and recognizes the importance of learning to enhance the chances of success and the development of plans and programs, especially in the activation of OL process.
2. The need to focus on knowledge management processes to achieve their interaction and integration with other learning processes, and the establishment of the center of its mission of knowledge management by watching what others are doing, through referential comparison and best practices.

3. Emphasis on investment learning in enhancing the chances of success to increase the efficiency of interaction with other learning processes through the promotion of senior management of learning. Add to this development through the use of active listening feedback, open channels of communication, the adoption of the approaches of teamwork and enabling individuals on thinking and performance skills.
4. Continuous promoting of modern technological applications and good investment at full power, combined with learning and knowledge management programs to facilitate decision-making and implementation processes. Add to this support training programs and the establishment of an integrated information system at the corporate level.
5. Continuous promotion of policies that seek to empower individuals, particularly through the adoption of decentralization and delegation of authority and the alleviation of laws and regulations to enable the organization to have initiative and move towards their goals more freely exploiting opportunities for success.
6. Expanding the powers of management organizations in selecting and attracting workers according to competence and maturity and the need to lay off the excess in the number of personnel leading to achieve effective performance.
7. The need to inform organizations about owning a learning organization characteristics, important strategic option for survival and success in a turbulent environment where everything is constantly changing through the simulation of advanced organizations.

7. Research Implications

The findings of the study should contribute to managers and practitioners becoming more aware of ES. In addition, management should encourage employees to express their relevant ideas, information and opinions.

The cultural dimensions such as appreciating the individuals, orientation to detail, team orientation and competition may lead to silence breaking, as they urge people to actively participate in matters of the organization, which reduces the degree of silence (O.Reilly, et al., 1991).

It is not easy to break silence climate of employees and their managers. The behavioral cycles that maintain OS will be hard to break in part because they are not subject to direct observation or discussion. To prevent silence from characterizing their organizations, leaders should not only permit, but reward, employees who come forward with sensitive or risky information, and should create formal mechanisms through which employees can speak up anonymously if they wish to do so (Reichers, et al. 1997).

The nature of silence behavior makes it difficult to break. This may be due to the fact that OS may be a result of lack of confidence in the organization (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

Silence climate has an impact on organization's ability to detect errors and learn and therefore, organizational effectiveness is negatively affected. ES behaviour can also create stress, cynicism, and dissatisfaction (Tamuz, 2001).

Breaking silence needs a vision which can provide a climate that helps in engagement and talking. Silence can be overcome through (1) encouraging employees to talk about work issues and choosing the appropriate time for that, (2) increasing employees' exchange and circulation of new ideas, (3) coordination between different departments and divisions within the organization, (4) provision of good channels of communication between the employees within the organization, (5) paying attention to the moral of the employees within the organization, (6) provision of organizational support for the exchange of ideas associated to labor issues, and (7) encouraging employees to creative thinking within the organization (Piderit & Ashford, 2003).

Breaking silence is also possible through the administration's desire to hear the views and suggestions of staff about problems and issues of work which they face. This is because the employee must feel safe when talking (Milliken et al., 2003).

Another way to encourage speaking up behaviour is to ensure communication opportunities and create formal systems for the transfer or exchange of information, concerns or ideas. Employees who have ideas or suggestions for improvement, who do not feel that they can bring these to their bosses, could submit them to a designated person who then presents the ideas for review. This would serve to create some potentially positive outcomes attached to the passage of ideas for process improvements up the hierarchy to

offset what are now seen as potentially negative outcomes of upsetting one's boss or being perceived as critical (Milliken et al., 2003).

Another way of breaking silence would be through the keenness of the leaders of organizations to fight or prevent any impediments to the transfer or exchange of upwards information relating to problems and issues of work (Edmondson, 2003).

Top managers and supervisors have to create a workplace where employees will feel safe to express their views and will be encouraged to offer their ideas and suggestions.

Therefore, top managers and supervisors should develop attitudes and engage in behaviours that would create a psychologically safety net for their employees. (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

There are some tools that can be used for the purpose of breaking OS. They are (1) the need to motivate employees to talk and provide their opinions and suggestions about work problems, (2) developing effective communication channels which support exchange and transfer of ideas and information, and (3) the need to employ and attract talented employees especially those who have high levels of organizational commitment. This is because these employees have a high tendency to speak and participate in labor issues.

Thus, OS can be reduced or faced focusing on the selection and retention of this distinctive quality of the staff (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

Organizations today need not only to recruit but also to retain and motivate talented employees. Managers may consider OS as an important variable when they explore organizational climate and culture or when they want to create an environment where talented people would choose to remain or wish to join. These practical implications are also important in a change context where the "truth" must be heard in order to be able to effectively implement and institutionalize the change and improve the existing situation (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

Finally, employees are regarded as major sources of change, creativity, learning, and innovation, which are critical factors to the success of organizations (Liu, et al. 2009).

8. Limitations and Future Research

There are some limitations of this study. They are (1) data was gathered from one private sector in Egypt. Therefore, the findings of this research need to be evaluated with this in mind. The survey answers are related to the perception of employees at that moment, (2) the respondents are unwilling to answer the questionnaires accurately. Therefore, before distributing questionnaires among respondents, we attempted to describe the positive effects of the results of this research on their work-life quality and satisfying their needs, (3) the current study is about cause and effect relationship among research variables; maybe there are other factors that affect research variables, which need to be identified.

There are several areas for future research. They are (1) identifying factors affect employees' silence; (2) identifying the effects of employees' silence on job satisfaction and organizational commitment (3) identifying the effects of leadership style on employees' silence, (4) identifying the effects of demographic variables on employees' silence, (5) identifying the relationship between organizational culture and OS, (6) identifying the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and OS, (7) identifying the relationship between organizational success and OS, (8) identifying the relationship between organizational excellence and OS (9) silence motivations (defensive silence, relations supportive silence, de facto silence, the silence of negligence) in service organizations, (10) the relationship between silence and organizational justice within business organizations, (11) comparing determinants of silence in the production and service organizations, and (12) the relationship between the determinants of OS and work involvement.

9. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, OS is evident quite in many organizations. This research expanded on previous research which conceptualized OS.

Moreover, the empirical evidence gathered makes a strong case for conceptualizing and examining OS. Additionally, this research demonstrated that this covert and seemingly ambiguous phenomenon can be measured. Although more work is needed in the area of OS, it appears that this research has effectively set the stage for further empirical examination.

In this research, most of the employees felt that the common reasons for ES are derived from administrative and organizational factors. This results are consistent with the previous researchers who

found that the most common reason for choosing to remain silent is "administrational and organizational reasons" (Cakici, 2008).

The managers hold the key role on ES since they determine the policies and organizational decisions. They have the power to establish an internal mechanism in order to remove any administrative and organizational reasons for ES allowing employees to speak up explicitly (Cakici, 2008).

Establishing an appropriate reward system for creative ideas and facilitating development and skill-building training can break ES in organizations. Additionally, reorientation of rules, dissemination of collaborative studies, re-structuring the harvesting of institutional knowledge and programs aimed at improving human resources management for executives are very important in minimizing the ES. Reassuring trust and rebuilding the communication bridges will help to increase the performance of an organization (Panahi et al., 2012).

OS can appear in different forms. Employees, based on acquiescence, may not express their views and opinions openly in the face of the management in the organizations; withhold their ideas intentionally because of fear or urge for self-protection or opt for remaining silence for the sake of other colleagues' well-being. The employees in the mentioned departments of the company under study chose to remain silent and not speak up to the upper management due to similar reasons (Yıldız, 2013).

OS not only results in low levels of morale, lack of confidence, disloyalty, stress and employees leaving, but also constitutes a barrier to the establishment of a healthy feedback mechanism. This situation can lead to unhealthy communication and serious distortions in, or non-existence of the knowledge on which managers base their decisions and can lead to flawed decisions (Yıldız, 2013).

OS makes the employees feel that they are unvalued (Nikolaou et al, 2011). The employees are trying to make sense of self-efficacy or competency. Managers, in addition of believing in teamwork must create a climate in which employees are not always unanimously agreed together because the conformity results in formation of OS. Gaining acceptance in the group, refraining from expressing opinions and comments and appropriate decision making in accordance with the environment are some reasons of leading to unanimously agreement together. So employees should always be ask to speak, offer views and news in order to remove OS (Tahmasebi1, et al., 2013).

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